

THE INFLUENCE OF THE SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN OF EARLY SCHOOL AGE

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In today's globalization process, one of the most urgent tasks facing the education system is to educate the younger generation as a comprehensively developed person. In particular, the issue of developing the personal characteristics of children of primary school age is being considered at the level of state policy [2, p.18] The latest resolutions and decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan pay special attention to the development of school education, strengthening psychological services, and revealing the personal potential of students. Primary school age is one of the important periods in a person's life, during which a child begins to acquire knowledge, adapt to social roles, and think independently. Therefore, the socio-psychological environment plays a decisive role in the sustainable development of a child's personality. [6, p.72] The theoretical views of scientists such as Vygotsky, J. Piaget, and E. Erikson deeply reveal the importance of the social environment in child psychology. The article examines the positive and negative aspects of the social environment in the formation of a child as a personality. [4, p.112]

Several methods were used in the study. Each method was supported not only by scientific foundations, but also by practical examples. Using this method, scientific literature, psychological articles and monographs on the topic were studied. For example, L.S. Vygotsky's work 'Thinking and Speech', J. Piaget's views on the cognitive development of a child, and E. Erikson's theory of psychosocial development were taken as a basis. These theoretical sources helped to deeply understand the influence of the socio-psychological environment on the development of a child's personality. [7, p.201]

2. Observation. The behavior of primary school students during the lesson and during breaks was regularly observed. In this process, their relationship with classmates, trust in the teacher, and the characteristics of their behavior in the team were noted.

3. Questionnaire. Special questionnaires were distributed among parents and teachers to determine the psychological characteristics of children. The questionnaires asked questions about the child's family environment, level of communication at home, school activities and relationships with peers. [5, p. 45]

4. Comparison. The behavior of children who grew up in a positive and negative environment was compared. Children raised in a healthy environment had higher self-esteem, more active participation in classes, and greater willingness to cooperate. On the contrary, children in environments with family conflict, neglect, or bullying were more likely to be shy, aggressive, or socially isolated. [5, p. 85]

This issue has been widely studied in the history of psychology. L.S. Vygotsky substantiated the role of the social environment in human development, while J. Piaget identified cognitive factors. E. Erikson, putting forward the psychosocial theory of the individual, emphasized the importance of social relations at school age. [1, p. 54]

The strengthening influence of the socio-psychological environment has not lost its power in modern times. Uzbek scientists V. Karimova, A. Askarov, Sh. Yusupova and others have emphasized the importance of school and family in maintaining support for children.

Figure 1. The influence of the socio-psychological environment on children of primary school age

The obtained results show that the socio-psychological personality of children in primary school is a crucial age. In a positive environment, creativity, empathy, cooperation and social activity are enhanced, while in a negative environment, passivity, fear, stability and aggression are increased.[5, p.147] Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to the creation of favorable conditions for their development through parents, teachers and psychologists. This situation places a responsibility on the shoulders of teachers, parents and psychologists. to him, preventing bullying, initiating social support and a healthy environment play a decisive role in the development of the child [2, p. 98].

In conclusion, the socio-psychological environment of children of primary school age is of decisive importance in the development of personality. Kindness in the family, a fair environment at school and healthy relationships with peers form the personality of the child in a harmonious way. Therefore, school psychologists, teachers and parents need to work together to create positive conditions. Therefore, creating a positive psychological environment in educational institutions and families is an urgent task. This will ensure the healthy psychological development of the future generation.

References

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